

Supplementary Materials for:

CONTRIBUTIONS OF MANGROVE CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION IN INDONESIA

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Figure S1. The major islands/regions in Indonesia.

Figure S2. The total ecosystem carbon stocks (TECS) of mangroves of Indonesia based upon region. The total sample size includes data from 54 sites. Vertical bars represent one standard error. Data are from Arifanti et al. (2019), Donato et al. (2011), Kauffman et al. (2020), and Murdiyarso et al. (2015).

Figure S3. Total net mangrove deforestation area by primary regions in Indonesia.

Figure S4. Total emissions and removals (Tg CO₂e) from mangrove forest change in 2009-2019 by primary regions in Indonesia.

Figure S5. The annual net emissions from 2009-2019, mangrove forest reference level (FRL) and potential emissions reduction pathways in mangrove ecosystems in Indonesia. Compared to the FRL, avoided mangrove deforestation and degradation pathway (green line) has higher potential to reduce emissions than restoration pathway (orange line).

Table S1. Ecosystem carbon stocks (Mg C ha⁻¹) of intact Indonesian mangroves (N=54).

Parameter	Mean	SE	Range	95% Confidence Interval
Total ecosystem Carbon	1,063.10	46.60	408-2208	91.40
Belowground Carbon	884.70	40.80	290 - 2076	79.90
Aboveground Carbon	178.60	15.70	14-501	30.70
Tree Mass	159.90	15.80	2-460	30.90
Downed Wood	18.70	15.70	0 - 85	4.60

Table S2. Aboveground C stocks (AGC), belowground C stocks (BGC) and total ecosystem C stocks (TECS) in secondary mangrove forests in Indonesia

	AGC (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	BGC (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	TECS (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
Mean	73.63	630.95	704.57
SE	13.31	54.23	63.01
N (sites)	8	8	8

Table S3. Emission factor calculation for primary mangrove conversion to other land uses

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
Region	Total ecosystem carbon stocks (TECS) (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	N	Conversion Stock Loss (51%) of TECS primary forest (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	ΔNEP forest to pond (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	EF (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [3] + [4]	EF (Mg CO ₂ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [[3] + [4]] *3.67
Country-wide	1,063.10	54.00	542.20	10.20	552.38	2027.20
Java	586.70	2.00	299.20	10.20	309.42	1135.60
Kalimantan	998.40	27.00	509.20	10.20	519.38	1906.10
Papua	1,209.90	13.00	617.00	10.20	627.25	2302.00
Sulawesi	938.40	6.00	478.60	10.20	488.78	1793.80
Sumatra	1,319.10	6.00	672.70	10.20	682.94	2506.40

Table S4. Emission factor calculation for primary mangrove conversion to secondary mangroves

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
Region	TECS of primary mangroves (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	TECS secondary forest (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	Carbon loss - primary to secondary mangrove (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [1] – [2]	ΔNEP (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	EF (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [3]+[4]	EF (Mg CO ₂ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [[3]+[4]]*3.67
Country wide	1,063.07	747.89	315.17	0.0	315.20	1,156.70
Java	586.70	415.97	170.74	0.0	170.70	626.60
Kalimantan	998.44	701.41	297.03	0.0	297.00	1,090.10
Papua	1,209.90	852.57	357.33	0.0	357.30	1,311.40
Sulawesi	938.43	659.14	279.29	0.0	279.30	1,025.00
Sumatra	1,319.13	929.63	389.50	0.0	389.50	1,429.50

Table S5. Emission factor calculation for secondary mangrove conversion to other land uses

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Region	TECS secondary forest (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	Conversion stock loss from secondary mangroves (29% of TECS) (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	ΔNEP (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	EF (Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [2]+[3]	EF (Mg CO ₂ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) Eq: [[2]+[3]]*3.67
Country wide	747.89	216.89	10.20	227.10	833.40
Java	415.97	120.63	10.20	130.80	480.10
Kalimantan	701.41	203.41	10.20	213.60	783.90
Papua	852.57	247.25	10.20	257.40	944.80
Sulawesi	659.14	191.15	10.20	201.40	739.00
Sumatra	929.63	269.59	10.20	279.80	1,026.80

Table S6. Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MoEF) land cover accuracy assessment

Year	Land Cover Class	Accuracy (%)		
		User Accuracy	Producer Accuracy	Overall Accuracy
1990	Forest	90.6	91.2	89.1
	Non-Forest	86.7	85.8	
1996	Forest	90.7	90.1	88.8
	Non-Forest	86.2	87	
2000	Forest	92.6	91	91.2
	Non-Forest	89.5	91.3	
2003	Forest	92.2	91.6	91.4
	Non-Forest	90.5	91.2	
2006	Forest	91.8	91.4	91.4
	Non-Forest	90.9	91.3	
2009	Forest	92.2	91.2	91.7
	Non-Forest	91.2	92.2	
2011	Forest	92.1	91.5	91.9
	Non-Forest	91.7	92.3	
2012	Forest	92.1	91.8	92.1
	Non-Forest	92.1	92.4	
2013	Forest	92.1	91.7	92.1
	Non-Forest	92.2	91.5	
2014	Forest	91.8	91.9	91.2
	Non-Forest	92.5	92.4	
2015	Forest	91.6	91.9	92.1
	Non-Forest	92.5	92.3	
2016	Forest	92.8	90.1	91.9
	Non-Forest	91.2	93.6	

Source: <https://nfms.menlhk.go.id/download/buku-akurasi-data-penutupan-lahan-nasional-tahun-1990-2016>

Table S7. Cumulative emission reduction projection potential (Tg CO₂e) of the Indonesian mangroves (2020 - 2030).

Sub-Categories	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024	2024-2025	2025-2026	2026-2027	2027-2028	2028-2029	2029-2030
Avoiding Mangroves Deforestation and Degradation	32.16	64.33	96.49	128.66	160.82	192.98	225.15	257.31	289.47	321.64
Reforestation	7.34	21.17	35	48.84	55.57	62.31	69.04	75.78	82.51	89.25
Avoiding Mangroves Deforestation and Degradation, Reforestation	39.50	85.50	131.49	177.49	216.39	255.29	294.19	333.09	371.99	410.89

Supplementary Text

Detailed methods to measure C stocks (Kauffman & Donato, 2012)

At each of the sampled mangrove sites, total ecosystem C stocks were determined in 6 different plots established 20–25 m apart along a 100–125m transect positioned perpendicular to the marine or riverine ecotone (Kauffman and Donato 2012). At each site, total ecosystem C stocks was derived from quantification of standing tree biomass (above and belowground), downed wood, and soils to the depths of the marine sands/bedrock.

Fixed-volume soil samples were collected to determine bulk density and carbon concentration. This was conducted using a semi-cylindrical peat auger with a radius of ≈ 6.4 -cm. When soils were >3 m in depth calculation of soil C pools were limited to 3 m. The concentration of C was determined by the dry combustion method (induction furnace). Bulk density and C concentration were then combined with plot-specific soil depth measurements to determine the soil C stocks.